

Optimizing Advanced Air Mobility Operations in a Corridor Network

Felipe Cordera, Alexandre Jacquillat, Spencer McDonald

Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge MA, fcordera@mit.edu; alexjacq@mit.edu; mcdonst@mit.edu

Abstract. Electric vertical-takeoff-and-landing (eVTOL) vehicles are paving the way toward Advanced Air Mobility (AAM). AAM systems are expected to rely on corridor networks, where en-route separation and directional flow management are essential to ensure safe and efficient operations. This paper develops a tractable optimization framework for AAM operations that jointly determines vehicle dispatching and routing, four-dimensional flight trajectories, and flow directionality in capacitated corridors. We formulate an integer optimization model in a time–space–lane network that exploits a subpath structure at the flight level. We solve it via column generation to decompose vehicle dispatching and corridor flow decisions in a master problem and flight trajectories in a pricing problem, using a tailored backward label-setting algorithm. Our method scales to realistic instances with up to 50 vertiports, 2,000 corridor conjunctions, and hundreds of trip requests. Results demonstrate that the integrated optimization methodology can provide significant benefits as compared to benchmarks, resulting in higher operating profits and larger demand coverage.

Funding: This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 1745302.

Key words: Advanced air mobility, Integer optimization, Air traffic management, Vehicle routing

1. Introduction

Major cities are facing critical challenges to meet mobility needs and environmental targets in the face of ever-growing population and urbanization. Existing transportation systems often operate at capacity, contributing to urban congestion and greenhouse gas emissions. Moreover, legacy transportation systems are heavily reliant on available infrastructure, resulting in limited mobility options in some neighborhoods. Therefore, city operators are eager to adopt new technologies and develop new operating solutions toward efficient and sustainable mobility.

One opportunity lies in Advanced Air Mobility (AAM), defined by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) as “a safe and efficient aviation transportation system that will [...] operate and transport passengers or cargo at lower altitudes within urban and suburban areas.” A prominent science fiction topic, AAM has become increasingly viable with the development of electric vertical-takeoff-and-landing (eVTOL) vehicles. The AAM industry has been attracting large investments, with more than 300 eVTOL prototypes under certification and a multibillion-dollar market potential (McKinsey & Co. 2022). Yet, AAM raises its own questions in terms of vehicle certification, operating protocols, weather avoidance, noise regulation, and infrastructure design—highlighted both by the White House’s National Aeronautics Science & Technology Priorities (White House 2023) and the AIAA’s Challenges to the Commercialization of Advanced Air Mobility report (AIAA Certification Task Force 2025) as critical barriers to adoption. Among these, one of the most pressing issues involves the safe operation of very high densities of passenger-carrying flights in capacitated airspace environments.

As a first step toward this objective, Concepts of Operations (ConOps) from NASA (2020) and the FAA (2023) proposed a system architecture with designated corridors to enforce vertical and horizontal separation requirements without overloading already-strained air traffic control systems. As a result, emerging AAM systems combine elements of air transportation (e.g., vertiports for vehicle takeoff, landing, and charging), urban mobility (e.g., on-demand point-to-point dispatch and

routing), and corridor-based operations (e.g., capacity management in uni-directional lanes whose direction can be dynamically adjusted). This integration creates a complex operational environment that requires new decision-support tools. In response, this paper develops a tractable methodology to optimize vehicle dispatching and routing, four-dimensional (spatiotemporal) flight trajectories, and flow directionality in capacitated en-route corridors, and applies it to inform strategic AAM planning and policy decisions.

1.1. Background

Advances in propulsion technologies have enabled the development of eVTOL aircraft (Figure 1). Sample designs include vectored thrust, tilt-wing configurations; lift-cruise designs with independent thrusters; and multicopter designs with motors and propellers. Technical characteristics include multi-passenger payloads (4–6 seats per aircraft), high speeds (50–200 miles per hour), and long flying ranges (20–250 miles). Operating costs are projected to fall around \$2.50–4.50 per seat-mile in the near term and \$0.50–2.50 in the long term, as compared to \$6–8 for helicopters, enabling scalable AAM operations at affordable price points.

Figure 1 Sample eVTOL designs (Vertical Flight Society 2023).

From a system-wide standpoint, ConOps from NASA (2020) and the FAA (2023) outline emerging AAM operations. Four elements are particularly important:

- *Vertiport infrastructure.* Vertiports allow eVTOL vehicles to take off and land. Throughput will be restricted by operating rules surrounding takeoffs and landings, akin to runway capacity at airports. In addition, idle eVTOL aircraft will charge their batteries at vertiports, so throughput will also be restricted by the number of parking spaces and recharging times, akin to gate capacities.
- *Point-to-point operations.* AAM systems will provide on-demand services with small-capacity vehicles across point-to-point networks, as opposed to scheduled services in high-capacity aircraft across hub-and-spoke networks in legacy air transportation systems. These operations may require accommodating up to thousands of flights per hour in a capacitated airspace (Booz Allen Hamilton 2018, Airbus 2018). To manage operating complexity, AAM operators will be in charge of vehicle dispatching and maintaining safe separations with no or minimal air traffic control interventions.
- *Corridor networks.* Initial AAM systems will rely on dedicated corridors to enable safe and efficient operations, acting as “sky highways.” Each corridor will comprise multiple uni-directional lanes to enforce vertical separation, and horizontal separation requirements must also be enforced. The direction of flow in each corridor-lane can be dynamically adjusted to maximize throughput.
- *Weather closure.* AAM systems are not expected to operate in poor weather (Goodrich and Theodore 2021). Flights will therefore need to be re-routed accordingly or canceled altogether.

1.2. Literature Review

Developments in eVTOL technologies have generated extensive research toward AAM (Garrow et al. 2020, Schweiger and Preis 2022, Brunelli et al. 2023, Lu et al. 2025). A vast research thread in aeronautics focuses on the development of eVTOL vehicle technologies, such as electric propulsion systems (Patterson et al. 2012), vehicle configurations (Brown and Harris 2018), and operational vs. economic trade-offs (Ha et al. 2019). On the demand side, surveys have been used to estimate customers' willingness to pay (Binder et al. 2018), mode choices between self-driving, autonomous cars and AAM (Garrow et al. 2019), and passengers' vertiport selection behavior for integrated AAM-airline services (Zhao et al. 2025). Another thread of research characterizes system-wide implications in terms of system certification, infrastructure, traffic management, and noise (Vascik and Hansman 2017).

At a strategic level, a key research question lies in the design of vertiport and corridor networks. Wu and Zhang (2021) optimized vertiport locations to minimize the generalized cost of travel between AAM and ground transportation. Kotwicz Herniczek et al. (2022) proposed AAM corridor designs by trading off airspace density, complexity, and flexibility. Rath and Chow (2022) used clustering to locate vertiports near demand hotspots. Wang et al. (2022a) developed a mixed-integer non-linear optimization methodology for vertiport planning, capturing the downstream impact on vehicle operations and passenger demand. Volakakis and Mahmassani (2024) proposed a facility-location framework for vertiport siting based on demand clustering and coverage optimization. Jiang et al. (2025) developed a demand-driven vertiport planning model combining discrete-choice demand estimation with multiobjective facility-location optimization. To retain tractability, these studies require simplifications on tactical AAM operations, by ignoring vehicle routing dynamics or approximating them via network flows or queueing networks. Our paper instead considers a fixed network of vertiports and corridors and focuses on optimizing tactical operations with explicit spatio-temporal granularity, as opposed to relying on aggregated demand and routing inputs.

Within AAM operations, several studies have developed algorithms to support safe and efficient eVTOL operations. Mueller et al. (2017) and Thipphavong et al. (2018) defined operational concepts, technologies, and procedures for high-density flight operations. Bosson and Lauderdale (2018) studied the integration of AAM operations into legacy air transportation systems. Pradeep and Wei (2018) developed heuristics for arrival trajectories at vertiports. Kleinbekman et al. (2020) proposed airspace design and scheduling algorithms to optimize eVTOL arrivals. Bharadwaj et al. (2021) incorporated safety constraints to minimize conflicts. Liu et al. (2026) integrated take-off sequencing and trajectory optimization to coordinate aircraft merging from a vertiport into a corridor. Rather than focusing on flight-level trajectory control, our paper considers network-wide AAM operations.

In a related setting, Li et al. (2020) used simulation to evaluate AAM operational performance. Shihab et al. (2019) optimized vehicle dispatching to compare scheduled and on-demand operations. Ale-Ahmad and Mahmassani (2021) proposed a location-allocation-routing problem to match passengers to vertiports. Chin et al. (2021, 2023) devised fairness metrics and congestion management protocols for AAM systems. Wang et al. (2022b) developed heuristics to minimize congestion and complexity. Sun et al. (2023) optimized aircraft assignment and routing under capacity and demand uncertainty using two-stage stochastic optimization with fairness and risk management objectives. More recently, Ko and Ahn (2025) developed a scheduling framework for on-demand eVTOL operations that accounts for battery dynamics, charging infrastructure, and vertiport throughput constraints. Our paper augments this literature in both scale and scope by considering larger networks and modeling tactical operations in granular corridor networks with endogenous flow directionality.

In particular, dynamically adjusting corridor-lane directions can help manage congestion and capacity. Similar flow-management structures arise in other transportation settings, such as maritime shipping (Lübbecke et al. 2019), railway corridors (Zinder et al. 2018), and road closures (Hua et al. 2019). However, these formulations typically focus on vehicle scheduling with exogenous routing inputs, whereas AAM operations require jointly optimizing flow directionality with vehicle dispatching and four-dimensional flight trajectories across the corridor network.

From a broader optimization standpoint, the dispatching and routing components of AAM operations relate to the Dial-a-Ride Problem (DARP), which optimizes routing decisions to serve origin–destination demand (see, e.g., Cordeau 2006, Qu and Bard 2015, Zhang et al. 2023). Espinoza et al. (2008a,b) studied the dial-a-flight problem, a precursor to AAM that adapts these routing ideas to air transportation settings. Related work has also considered vehicle routing problems with congestion effects, typically modeling travel-time variations as exogenous inputs (Florio et al. 2021, Liu et al. 2023, Dabia et al. 2013, Fleischmann et al. 2004). However, AAM operations depart from these formulations in a fundamental way. AAM requires routing decisions to be coordinated with en-route capacity management and dynamically adjustable corridor directions, whereas most DARP formulations assume routing decisions in unconstrained networks or capture congestion through exogenous travel-time variations. In addition, AAM operations may be affected by disruptions such as weather closures, which further interact with routing and network decisions.

The problem also relates to the Air Traffic Flow Management (ATFM) literature, which optimizes air transportation operations to absorb delays at departure airports and en-route rather than in terminal airspace (Odoni 1987). Extensive research has developed ATFM models in a variety of settings, including single-airport problems (Richetta and Odoni 1993, Terrab and Odoni 1993), multi-airport networks (Vranas et al. 1994, Bertsimas and Stock Patterson 1998, Bertsimas et al. 2011b), collaborative airline settings (Vossen and Ball 2006), stochastic environments (Ball et al. 2003), equity-aware formulations (Barnhart et al. 2012, Bertsimas and Gupta 2016), and passenger-centric models (Jacquillat 2022). However, AAM operations depart from this literature in several important ways: operations occur in corridor-based high-density airspace networks rather than sector-based airspace, vertiports introduce parking and charging capacities in addition to departure and arrival constraints, and vehicles are dispatched and routed on demand rather than following pre-planned flight schedules.

Taken together, these characteristics highlight the need to jointly manage vehicle routing decisions and en-route capacity constraints in AAM corridor networks. From an optimization perspective, this problem lies at the intersection of the DARP literature—focusing on routing vehicles to serve origin–destination demand—and the ATFM literature—focusing on coordinating traffic flows under airspace capacity constraints. However, existing approaches in these two streams are typically studied separately. AAM operations require integrating these perspectives by jointly optimizing vehicle dispatching, modular flight trajectories, and corridor flow management—including endogenous corridor directionality—within capacitated corridor networks.

1.3. Contributions and Outline

This paper develops a scalable optimization methodology for AAM operations in capacitated and uni-directional corridor networks. This problem can be viewed as a *dial-a-ride problem with time windows, operating capacities in a granular en-route network, and endogenous flow directionality*. In this sense, our work integrates elements of both the DARP literature and the ATFM literature. We augment the former by optimizing four-dimensional flight trajectories between origins and destinations while also determining the directionality of operations in each corridor lane. While

we augment the latter by modeling operating restrictions and traffic interactions within corridor-based AAM networks, together with vehicle dispatching and routing dynamics. Leveraging flight-based trajectory variables, we develop a column generation approach that decomposes (i) dial-a-ride dynamics and air conflict management in a master problem from (ii) en-route trajectory generation in a pricing problem. We also develop a data-driven experimental setup to demonstrate the scalability and benefits of the proposed methodology. Ultimately, this paper presents one of the first optimization studies supporting emerging AAM operations in corridor networks and informing the design of AAM technologies and policies. Specifically, this paper makes the following contributions:

- **A flight-based integer optimization model for AAM corridor operations (Section 2).** The tactical AAM operations problem optimizes vehicle dispatching, flight trajectories, flow management and directionality decisions in a granular network (i.e., a network of vertiports and corridor conjunctions, rather than a mere network of vertiports), and passenger service. We develop a flight-based integer optimization model in a time–space–lane network that captures coordination requirements while retaining high discretization fidelity and a tight linear relaxation.

- **A column generation algorithm to solve large-scale practical instances (Section 3).** By generating flight-based variables iteratively, this algorithm decomposes the dial-a-ride dynamics and air conflict management in a master problem, and flight trajectories in a corridor network in a pricing problem. The pricing problem features a shortest-path structure with edge costs that depend on the destination. We exploit this structure to design a backward label-setting algorithm (from destination to origin), as opposed to a traditional forward algorithm (from origin to destination). This algorithm enables considerable speedups.

- **A high-fidelity data-driven experimental setup for emerging AAM systems (Section 4).** Evaluating operational concepts for emerging AAM systems requires constructing realistic experimental environments. We develop such a framework for the New York metropolitan area by generating demand inputs using a discrete-choice model based on U.S. Census and Google Maps data, weather inputs from aviation ground observations, and network data from the National Airspace System inspired by ConOps from FAA (2023). This setup provides a realistic simulation environment for large-scale AAM operations. Data, source code, and visualizations are made available online.

- **Computational scalability and operational insights for large-scale AAM systems (Section 5).** Results show that our methodology scales to realistic problem sizes, enabled by the flight-based formulation, column generation algorithm, and acceleration strategies. In particular, our method solves to near optimality (within a 1% gap) instances involving up to 50 vertiports, 2,000 corridor conjunctions, and hundreds of demand requests, significantly outperforming off-the-shelf methods. Complementary large-scale data-driven experiments in the New York metropolitan area highlight the operational benefits of optimizing modular flight trajectories and corridor directionality in capacitated networks. These results show that integrated optimization can improve profit and demand coverage by up to 60%, underscoring its value for emerging AAM systems. A bottleneck analysis further reveals that AAM throughput depends not only on vertiport capacities but also on en-route restrictions: legacy corridor networks and horizontal separation requirements reduce demand and profitability by about 30%, while adverse weather can cause an additional 20% loss. These findings provide insight for AAM planning, policy, and infrastructure investment decisions.

2. Model Formulation

We formulate an integer optimization model for AAM operations in a capacitated corridor network. Inputs characterize passenger demand, eVTOL vehicle performance, and network topology. The

model outputs: (i) time-varying flow directionality in each corridor-lane; (ii) vehicle dispatching and routing across vertiports; (iii) four-dimensional (time–space–lane) flight trajectories within the corridor network; and (iv) passenger service decisions (accept/reject and waiting times). The optimization combines elements of a dial-a-ride problem (vehicle dispatching, time windows), elements of a flow management problem (vehicle trajectory optimization, en-route capacities, and resulting coordination requirements between vehicle operations), and new elements due to endogenous uni-directional travel (which add a discrete optimization structure and linking constraints to the problem). We develop two formulations of the problem: a flight-based flow (FBF) formulation that serves as the core of our modeling framework, and a corridor-based flow (CBF) formulation used as a benchmark and described in Appendix A. Table 1 summarizes notation.

Table 1 Input data and decision variables.

Notation	Description
Network inputs	
\mathcal{I}	Set of corridor conjunctions and vertiports (graph nodes)
$\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathcal{I}$	Subset of vertiports
$\mathcal{C} \subseteq \mathcal{I} \times \mathcal{I}$	Subset of corridors (graph arcs)
$\delta_d^+(i)/\delta_d^-(i)$	Set of corridors entering/leaving node i in direction d (e.g., east vs. west)
\mathcal{L}	Set of vertical lanes
\mathcal{T}	Discretized time periods (in increments of κ)
d_c	Length of corridor $c \in \mathcal{C}$
Δ_c	Time to traverse corridor c (in periods)
v	Vehicle speed
h_ℓ	Altitude of lane ℓ
ζ_c^e, ζ_c^w	Eastern and western endpoints of corridor c
Vertiport inputs	
Ψ_i	Initial number of eVTOLs at vertiport i
Ω_i	Parking capacity at vertiport i
Γ_i	Arrival/departure capacity at vertiport i
τ	Vehicle turnaround time
Demand inputs	
\mathcal{P}	Set of passenger requests
\mathcal{P}_{ij}^t	Subset of requests from vertiport i to j at time t
M_n	Maximum wait time for request n
π_n	Revenue from request n
Route inputs	
\mathcal{R}	Set of all feasible two-dimensional routes r between vertiports
$\mathcal{D}_{ij} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$	Routes departing from vertiport i and arriving at vertiport j
$\mathcal{A}_i \subseteq \mathcal{R}$	Routes that arrive at vertiport i
$\mathcal{E}_c, \mathcal{W}_c \subseteq \mathcal{R}$	Routes that traverse corridor c eastward/westward
$\mathcal{N}_i \subseteq \mathcal{R}$	Routes that pass through conjunction node i
$\Phi(r, i), \mathcal{K}(r, i)$	Time required / corridors traversed by route r to reach node i
Variables	
$F_{r\ell}^t$	1 if a vehicle departs on route r in lane ℓ at time t
$D_{ij\ell}^t$	1 if a vehicle departs from vertiport i toward j in lane ℓ at time t
$A_{i\ell}^t$	1 if a vehicle arrives at vertiport i from lane ℓ at time t
$E_{c\ell}^t, W_{c\ell}^t$	1 if a vehicle flies corridor c eastward/westward in lane ℓ at time t
$e_{c\ell}^s, w_{c\ell}^s$	1 if lane ℓ in corridor c operates eastward/westward during time-window s
R_n, T_{nk}	1 if request n is rejected / served after k waiting periods
I_i^t	Number of idle vehicles at vertiport i at time t

2.1. Problem Description

Corridor network and structure. The key feature of the problem lies in the capacitated corridor network. In legacy air transportation systems, most airspace is controlled by air navigation service providers (e.g., the US Federal Aviation Administration). To handle high-density volumes in AAM, NASA (2020) and FAA (2023) have proposed to carve out sections of airspace that will be operated along *corridors*, akin to “sky highways” connecting the vertiports. Each corridor comprises multiple vertically separated lanes that can operate in either direction, enforcing vertical separation requirements by design (Figure 2). In each corridor-lane, vehicles travel in a single direction while AAM service providers maintain safe horizontal separations. Nonetheless, the direction of flow in each corridor-lane is not fixed in advance but dynamically determined as part of the optimization of AAM operations. Direction reversals require a short clearing period, mirroring idle times following runway configuration changes at airports (Bertsimas et al. 2011a, Jacquillat et al. 2017).

Figure 2 AAM corridor with four vertical lanes; two eastbound and two westbound (FAA 2023).

We represent the corridor system as a directed network $(\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{C})$, where the node set \mathcal{I} includes both capacitated *vertiports* (for takeoff and landing operations) and capacitated *corridor conjunctions* corresponding to intersections of corridors in the en-route airspace. Let $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ denote the subset of vertiport nodes. Each corridor is represented by arcs duplicated across vertical lanes. To capture flow directionality, we partition arcs according to a directional index d , which we refer to as “eastward” and “westward” (breaking ties arbitrarily for north–south directions). To retain realistic connectivity patterns, we assume that the total number of nodes scales at least linearly with the number of vertiports, i.e., $|\mathcal{I}| = O(|\mathcal{V}|^{q_1})$ with $q_1 \geq 1$, and that the number of arcs scales linearly to quadratically, i.e., $|\mathcal{C}| = O(|\mathcal{V}|^{q_2})$ with $1 \leq q_2 \leq 2$.

Time–altitude–expanded network. We represent AAM operations in a discretized four-dimensional time–space–lane network obtained by expanding the spatial corridor network across time periods and altitude lanes. Time–space network representations are widely used to model vehicle movements and resource constraints over time in transportation systems, including service network design (Crainic et al. 2016), air transportation (Lee et al. 2020), maritime shipping (Agarwal and Ergun 2008), railway scheduling (Liebchen 2008), and vehicle sharing (Zhang et al. 2021). In contrast, AAM operations require extending this representation with an additional lane dimension to represent vertical operations in corridor-based airspace.

We define a sufficiently granular time discretization over set \mathcal{T} so that horizontal separation requirements translate into a capacity of one vehicle per conjunction node per period. This representation preserves the temporal and spatial continuity of vehicle trajectories while capturing coordination requirements between flights. Additional capacity constraints impose vertiport takeoff, landing, and parking limits, and account for the idleness dynamics associated with changes in lane directionality required to preserve system safety.

Assumptions. Before proceeding, we make the following assumptions and simplifications:

- *Centralized operations.* AAM operations are managed by a centralized decision-maker. This paper therefore takes a system-wide view of AAM operations or the perspective of a single AAM service provider.

- *Fixed network topology.* The network topology is fixed, determining the sets of vertiports, corridors, and corridor conjunctions (along with their operating capacities). In the event of weather closures, we assume that the network is modified deterministically. This assumption is motivated by the short planning horizon, during which reliable weather forecasts may be available.

- *Passenger demand and pooling.* Passenger requests are treated as exogenous, so the model focuses on supply-side operational decisions. Requests are constructed as pooled groups that respect vehicle capacity limits. For simplicity, we consider a sequential approach where the AAM operator has already formed groups of passengers traveling together; pooling decisions themselves are not optimized in this paper, but could be integrated (Dogan and Jacquillat 2025).

- *Passenger service windows.* Each pooled request has a maximum waiting time reflecting service-level requirements in on-demand operations. These waiting times define time windows within which the request must be served.

- *Demand visibility and rolling horizon.* Passenger requests are assumed known for the full planning horizon. While business models for AAM operators remain uncertain, it is foreseeable that operators will require some advance visibility into passenger demand. In practice, the model is intended to be applied online in a rolling-horizon setting.

- *Homogeneous vehicles and turnaround times.* Vehicles are homogeneous and share a uniform turnaround time at vertiports. In legacy air transportation systems, turnaround times vary with aircraft type, passenger volume, and airport layout (Birolini and Jacquillat 2023). These factors are less pronounced in AAM systems with small-payload vehicles and compact vertiports. For simplicity, we do not track battery consumption explicitly; this can be justified by applying a conservative turnaround time that ensures full battery recharging.

- *Single-lane flights.* Each flight operates in a single lane without altitude changes. While vehicles could potentially change altitude in practice, such maneuvers would introduce additional operational complexity, safety risks, and potential discomfort for passengers.

2.2. Flight-based Flow (FBF) Formulation

We propose a set-partitioning formulation with flight-based variables to model flight trajectories through the AAM corridor network, building upon subpath-based dial-a-ride formulations (Alyasiry et al. 2019, Zhang et al. 2023, Martin-Iradi et al. 2024). The formulation defines a set \mathcal{R} of feasible two-dimensional (i.e., altitude-agnostic) routes connecting vertiports through ordered corridor sequences, and optimizes vehicle routing and dispatch, lane assignments, and flow directionality across the network.

Binary decision variables $F_{r\ell}^t$ indicate whether a flight departs along route $r \in \mathcal{R}$ using lane $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ at time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, thus encoding four-dimensional flight trajectories, while parameter $\Phi(r, i)$ quantifies the travel time from the departure vertiport of route r to node $i \in \mathcal{I}$. Note that flight-based variables ensure flow conservation at intermediate conjunction nodes (see Figure 3). We link these variables to

vertiport operations via departure/arrival variables $D_{ij\ell}^t$ and $A_{i\ell}^t$, and to eastward/westward corridor flows $E_{c\ell}^t$ and $W_{c\ell}^t$. We also define binary variables $e_{c\ell}^s$ and $w_{c\ell}^s$ to optimize flow directionality. The index s denotes a coarser time discretization spanning periods $t \in [s\Delta_c, (s+1)\Delta_c)$, where Δ_c denotes the time to traverse the corridor. Finally, service-level variables R_n and T_{nk} denote passenger requests rejected and delayed (by k periods), respectively; while I_i^t tracks the number of idle vehicles at each vertiport. The FBF formulation is as follows:

$$\min \sum_{n \in \mathcal{P}} \pi_n R_n + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} h_{\ell} A_{j\ell}^t + \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} d_c (E_{c\ell}^t + W_{c\ell}^t) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{r \in \mathcal{D}_{ij}} F_{r\ell}^t = D_{ij\ell}^t, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, j \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{i\}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{r \in \mathcal{A}_j} F_{r\ell}^{t-\Phi(r,j)} = A_{j\ell}^t, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{V}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{r \in \mathcal{E}_c} F_{r\ell}^{t-\Phi(r,\zeta_c^w)} = E_{c\ell}^t, \quad \sum_{r \in \mathcal{W}_c} F_{r\ell}^{t-\Phi(r,\zeta_c^e)} = W_{c\ell}^t, \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (4)$$

$$I_i^t = I_i^{t-1} + \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} A_{i\ell}^{t-\tau} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} D_{ij\ell}^t, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} A_{i\ell}^t + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} D_{ij\ell}^t \leq \Gamma_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (6)$$

$$I_i^t + \sum_{s=0}^{\tau-1} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} A_{i\ell}^{t-s} \leq \Omega_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{c \in \delta_e^+(i)} E_{c\ell}^t + \sum_{c \in \delta_w^+(i)} W_{c\ell}^t \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (8)$$

$$E_{c\ell}^t \leq e_{c\ell}^{\lfloor t/\Delta_c \rfloor}, \quad W_{c\ell}^t \leq w_{c\ell}^{\lfloor t/\Delta_c \rfloor}, \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (9)$$

$$e_{c\ell}^{s+u} + w_{c\ell}^s \leq 1, \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \lceil |\mathcal{T}|/\Delta_c \rceil\}, u \in \{-1, 0, 1\} \quad (10)$$

$$R_n + \sum_{k=0}^{M_n} T_{nk} = 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{P} \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{P}} \sum_{k=0}^{M_n} \mathbf{1}(n \in \mathcal{P}_{ij}^{t-k}) T_{nk} \leq \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} D_{ij\ell}^t, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{V} | i \neq j, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12)$$

$$I_i^0 = \Psi_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V} \quad (13)$$

$$F, D, A, E, W, e, w, R, T \text{ binary, } I \text{ integer.} \quad (14)$$

Equation (1) optimizes profit by minimizing revenue losses from rejected demand and operating costs associated with four-dimensional vehicle trajectories. Constraints (2)–(4) ensure consistency between routes and corridor flows. Constraint (5) maintains ground flow conservation at each vertiport; considering idle, arrival, and departure flows. Vertiport capacities limit the number of takeoffs and landings (Constraint (6)) and the number of idle and inbound vehicles (Constraint (7)).

The unit-capacity restriction in each conjunction–lane (Constraint (8)) ensures horizontal separation in the discretized time–space network. Constraints (9) ensure consistency between vehicle flows and corridor directionality decisions, and Constraint (10) enforces uni-directionality and a one-period changeover time when lanes reverse direction so that flow can “clear out” before some aircraft can travel in the other direction (e.g., if we operate eastward in period s , we can only operate westward in $s + 2$). Passenger service logic is defined by Constraints (11)–(12), which ensure that each request is either rejected or accepted with a feasible delay, while also allowing repositioning of idle vehicles when availability at other vertiports is insufficient. Finally, Constraint (13) initializes the network state, and Constraint (14) specifies variable domains.

Figure 3 FBF formulation: each route defines a sequence of corridors and conjunctions, with flow balance.

2.3. Benchmark: Corridor-based Flow (CBF) Formulation

We also consider a corridor-based flow formulation (CBF), which models vehicle movements using granular arc-level variables in the time–space–lane network and serves as a natural baseline (details in Appendix A). Compared with CBF, the flight-based formulation (FBF) exhibits three key differences related to travel-time fidelity, strength of linear relaxations, and model size.

Travel-time fidelity. Both formulations rely on a discretized time–space network, which can introduce approximation errors (Boland et al. 2017). In the CBF formulation, these discretization errors accumulate across corridors along a trajectory. In contrast, the FBF formulation applies rounding only once per trajectory, limiting the resulting error.

PROPOSITION 1. *For any route, the travel-time discretization error in the FBF formulation is at most one time step, whereas in CBF it can increase with the number of traversed corridors.*

Hereafter, to enable an apples-to-apples comparison, travel times are specified per corridor, and flight times equal the sum of their constituent corridor times (i.e., $\Phi(r, i) = \sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r, i)} \Delta_c$).

Strength of linear relaxations. The FBF formulation can be interpreted as a Dantzig–Wolfe reformulation of the CBF formulation, obtained by removing arc-level flow balance constraints and introducing route-based trajectory variables.

PROPOSITION 2. *The FBF formulation defines a Dantzig–Wolfe reformulation of CBF.*

This result establishes the formal link between the two formulations and underpins the column generation approach introduced in the next section. In particular, route-based variables allow operational restrictions defined at the flight level to be embedded directly within the route structure. As a result, extensions such as aircraft endurance limits or restrictions on the use of specific

corridors (e.g., due to weather conditions) can be incorporated naturally in the FBF formulation without introducing additional fractionality. By contrast, in the CBF formulation such restrictions must be enforced through additional constraints on arc-level flows, which may weaken the linear relaxation. In the current problem setting, however, the model does not include such route-level restrictions, and both formulations therefore yield the same linear relaxation value.

Model size. The FBF formulation removes corridor flow balance constraints, resulting in fewer constraints when the number of conjunction nodes grows faster than the number of vertiports. However, the number of flight-based variables grows exponentially with the number of conjunction nodes, motivating the column generation approach introduced in the next section.

3. Column Generation Algorithm

Our solution methodology employs a column generation algorithm that alternates between a Restricted Master Problem (RMP) and a Pricing Problem (PP) to iteratively generate flight-based variables with negative reduced cost—or prove that none exist. The algorithm solves the linear relaxation of the FBF formulation to optimality. Upon convergence, we solve the resulting FBF model to retrieve an integral solution. In practice, this procedure yields small optimality gaps (see Section 5). Otherwise, the column generation algorithm could also be embedded into a branch-and-price structure to guarantee integral optimality.

Rather than performing column generation over the route set \mathcal{R} , our approach expands route–lane–time combinations $(r, \ell, t) \in \mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{L} \times \mathcal{T}$. The PP identifies combinations with negative reduced cost, and the corresponding $F_{r\ell}^t$ variables are introduced into the RMP. This approach retains a compact formulation in the RMP, and provides flexibility to add granularity in selected subregions of $\mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{L} \times \mathcal{T}$ (e.g., by adding routes during some time periods to circumvent adverse weather but retaining coarser options elsewhere). This flexibility comes at the expense of a more complex pricing problem over all route–lane–time combinations.

Overall, the column generation procedure decomposes dial-a-ride and flow management dispatching decisions (in the RMP) from flight trajectory generation within the corridor network (in the PP). The procedure, outlined in Algorithm 1, comprises three main components: initialization, master problem, and pricing problem. Proposition 3 establishes the exactness of column generation with respect to the linear relaxation of the FBF formulation.

PROPOSITION 3. *The column generation algorithm terminates in a finite number of iterations with an optimal solution of the linear relaxation of the FBF formulation.*

Algorithm 1 Column generation algorithm

- Step 1.** Initialize route–lane–time combinations $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \mathcal{S}^0 \subseteq \mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{L} \times \mathcal{T}$ (Section 3.1)
 - Step 2.** Solve RMP; store incumbent primal solution and dual variables (Section 3.2)
 - Step 3.** Solve PP. If all reduced costs are non-negative, go to Step 4. Otherwise, expand the set \mathcal{S} with route–lane–time combinations with negative reduced costs; go to Step 2 (Section 3.3)
 - Step 4.** Solve restricted master problem via integer optimization.
-

3.1. Column Initialization

To accelerate convergence, we seed the master problem with a set of “promising” route–lane–time combinations, denoted by \mathcal{S}^0 . We consider two alternative initialization strategies:

1. *Shortest-route*: In uncapacitated corridor networks, flights would follow the shortest route r_{ij}^* between vertiports i and j . We therefore replicate all shortest routes, across all lanes and all time periods. Thus, we define initial columns

$$\mathcal{S}^0 = \{(r_{ij}^*, \ell, t) : (i, j) \in \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T}\}.$$

2. *Compatible-route*: To reduce directional conflicts, odd lanes handle eastbound (\mathcal{L}_e) and even lanes westbound (\mathcal{L}_w) traffic. For each vertiport pair, we include its shortest route in the corresponding directional subset. Thus, we define initial columns

$$\mathcal{S}^0 = \{(r_{ij}^*, \ell, t) : (i, j) \in \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}_{\chi(i,j)}, t \in \mathcal{T}\},$$

where $\chi(i, j) = e$ if vertiport j lies east of i , and $\chi(i, j) = w$ otherwise. Although some routes may momentarily reverse direction, this initialization yields high-quality columns and reduces conflicts in Constraint (10), enhancing computational efficiency of the column generation algorithm.

3.2. Restricted Master Problem (RMP)

The RMP is the linear relaxation of FBF restricted to the subset of flight-based variables $(r, \ell, t) \in \mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{L} \times \mathcal{T}$. It includes dual variables for all constraints that involve the flight-based variables, namely: (i) $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$ for vertiport flow constraints (2); (ii) $\kappa_{j\ell}^t$ for arrival constraints (3); and (iii) $\psi_{c\ell}^t$ and $\xi_{c\ell}^t$ for eastward and westward corridor flow constraints (4)–(5).

3.3. Pricing Problem (PP)

Let $i(r)$ and $j(r)$ denote the origin and destination vertiports of route $r \in \mathcal{R}$, respectively. The pricing problem searches through route–lane–time combinations (r, ℓ, t) , namely, subpaths that depart from vertiport i using lane ℓ at time t and arrive at vertiport j . It seeks combinations whose associated flight-based variables $F_{r\ell}^t$ have negative reduced cost. The reduced cost of $F_{r\ell}^t$ is:

$$\text{Reduced cost of } F_{r\ell}^t = \gamma_{i(r)j(r)\ell}^t + \kappa_{j(r)\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,j(r))} + \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}: r \in \mathcal{E}_c} \psi_{c\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,\zeta_c^w)} + \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}: r \in \mathcal{W}_c} \xi_{c\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,\zeta_c^e)}. \quad (15)$$

One complexity in this problem arises from destination-dependent arc costs. The corridor flow constraints are independent of the destination vertiport, so the corresponding dual variables, $\psi_{c\ell}^t$ and $\xi_{c\ell}^t$, depend only on the “current” corridor and time–lane state. This structure enables the duals to better price shared corridor capacity, by avoiding degenerate constraints enforced only for vehicles traveling to a specific destination. In contrast, the departure flow constraints depend not only on the departure vertiport, but also on the arrival vertiport to model passenger service. Consequently, the associated dual variables $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$ enter the pricing problem as destination-dependent arc costs that cannot be defined solely from local information.

To address this challenge, we represent each route–lane–time combination as a subpath in a four-dimensional time–space–lane network, also referred to as a time–altitude–expanded corridor network. Under this representation, the pricing problem becomes a shortest-path problem in a *destination-dependent time–space–lane network* (TSLN- j) for each arrival vertiport j . We show that any flight-based variable with destination j then maps into a unique path in TSLN- j , and vice versa. However, because arc costs depend on destination through $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$, the resulting shortest-path problem does not admit the standard arc-based decomposition typically exploited by label-setting algorithms. To overcome this difficulty, we propose a tailored backward label-setting algorithm to solve the pricing problem efficiently.

Destination-dependent time–space–lane network (TSLN- j). In the pricing problem, the time–space–lane network (TSLN) comprises two classes of nodes: (i) one node $N_{i\ell}^t$ corresponding to each physical node $i \in \mathcal{I}$, lane $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ and time $t \in \mathcal{T}$; and (ii) one node M_i for each vertiport $i \in \mathcal{V}$ corresponding to the flights that need to depart from i or that have arrived at i . Note that the dual variables $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$ depend on the current node $N_{i\ell}^t$, as well as the destination node M_j . Therefore, the arc costs in the network depend on the arrival vertiport j , and thus is referred to as “TSLN- j ”. Specifically, the TSLN- j comprises three categories of arcs:

1. *Departure arcs:* $M_i \rightarrow N_{i\ell}^t$ for all $i \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{j\}$, $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$, and $t \in \mathcal{T}$, with cost $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$.
2. *Arrival arcs:* $N_{j\ell}^t \rightarrow M_j$ for all $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ and $t \in \mathcal{T}$, with cost $\kappa_{j\ell}^t$.
3. *En-route corridor arcs:* for each corridor $c \in \mathcal{C}$, lane $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$, and time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, an eastward arc $N_{\zeta_c, \ell}^t \rightarrow N_{\zeta_c, \ell}^{t+\Delta_c}$ with cost $\psi_{c\ell}^t$, and a westward arc $N_{\zeta_c, \ell}^t \rightarrow N_{\zeta_c, \ell}^{t-\Delta_c}$ with cost $\xi_{c\ell}^t$.

The next proposition establishes the correctness of this representation by showing that there is a one-to-one correspondence between flight-based variables and paths in TSLN- j , implying that the pricing problem can be solved as a shortest-path problem.

PROPOSITION 4. *There is a bijection between any path p from M_i to M_j in TSLN- j and a flight-based variable $F_{r\ell}^t$ with route $r \in \mathcal{D}_{ij} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$, lane $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$, and departure time $t \in \mathcal{T}$. The reduced cost of $F_{r\ell}^t$ equals the sum of arc costs in p .*

Pricing via shortest paths. The Bellman–Ford algorithm computes shortest paths from a single source node to all other nodes in a network. In the TSLN- j , however, arc costs depend on the arrival vertiport through $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$. As a result, the shortest path can only be retrieved from a specific departure vertiport to the destination vertiport j at a time (Figure 4a). A natural *forward* algorithm would therefore loop over all vertiport pairs and solve $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{V}|^2)$ shortest-path problems (see Algorithm 3 in Appendix B).

Instead, to improve scalability, we propose a *backward* algorithm (Algorithm 2). Specifically, we apply the Bellman–Ford algorithm in a backward network constructed as the reverse of TSLN- j , denoted $\overline{\text{TSLN}}\text{-}j$. This network is obtained by flipping all arcs: each arc from node n to node m is transformed into an arc from m to n with the same weight. The algorithm then searches for “inverse” shortest paths from the destination vertiport j to origin vertiports i .

This construction allows us to exploit the single-source-to-all-nodes property of the Bellman–Ford algorithm. Whereas this property cannot be fully leveraged in the forward network because arc costs depend on both the origin and destination through $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$, in the backward network the arc costs only depend on the “source”, that is, on the arrival vertiport j . Running Bellman–Ford once from node M_j therefore yields shortest paths from j to all other vertiports simultaneously. Each backward path corresponds to a feasible forward route from i to j in the original network (see Figure 4).

Algorithm 2 Backward-pair label-setting algorithm

```

for  $j \in \mathcal{V}$  do
    Run the Bellman–Ford algorithm from node  $M_j$  in  $\overline{\text{TSLN}}\text{-}j$  ▷  $|\mathcal{V}|$  times
    for  $i \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{j\}$  do
        Use the path state to find the shortest path from  $M_j$  to  $M_i$ 
        From the backward path, retrieve the forward path from  $M_i$  to  $M_j$ 
        If the reduced cost is negative, add the  $(r, \ell, t)$  uplet to the set  $\mathcal{S}$ 
    end for
end for
    
```

Figure 4 Examples of forward and backward networks, with shortest paths shown in blue. In the forward network, the shortest path can only be obtained from M_i to M_j because of the γ_{ijl}^t edge weight. In the backward network, the inverse shortest path can simultaneously be obtained from M_j to M_i and from M_j to M_k .

This backward algorithm relates to bi-directional search methods (see, e.g., Righini and Salani 2006), but is designed here to circumvent the destination-dependent costs in the dynamic programming procedure rather than merely improving the efficiency of the shortest-path tree. Its exactness, established in Proposition 5, relies on the one-to-one mapping between forward and backward paths.

PROPOSITION 5. *The backward pricing algorithm terminates in $O(|\mathcal{V}|^{1+q_1+q_2}|\mathcal{T}|^2|\mathcal{L}|^2)$ iterations, whereas the forward algorithm terminates in $O(|\mathcal{V}|^{2+q_1+q_2}|\mathcal{T}|^2|\mathcal{L}|^2)$ iterations.*

In summary, the *backward label-setting* approach achieves the same guarantees as the forward algorithm while reducing the number of shortest-path computations from $|\mathcal{V}|^2$ to $|\mathcal{V}|$.

4. Experimental Setup

We leverage real-world data on commuting patterns, air mobility networks, and weather conditions to characterize emerging AAM systems—a challenging task given that these systems are not yet operational. We evaluate the methodology on synthetic instances to test scalability and complexity, and on data-driven instances (calibrated with publicly available information for the New York metropolitan area) to demonstrate the practical benefits of the integrated optimization framework. Data and code are made publicly available.¹

Nominal parameters. Simulations use 1–3 hour planning horizons, with an extra hour-long buffer to avoid boundary effects. We consider a flying speed of $v = 100$ mph, and a time discretization of $\kappa = 1$ minute. Thus, the number of periods to traverse each corridor becomes $\Delta_c = \max(\{\lfloor d_c / (v\kappa) \rfloor, 1\})$, which induces a minimum separation distance of 1.6 miles, in line with current projections. We assume a vertiport throughput of one arrival or departure per minute, consistently with corridor separations. Parking capacities range from 3 to 10 positions per vertiport, and the number of vertical lanes ranges from 2 to 8. Revenue of each request scales with the point-to-point distance between the origin and destination vertiports. All models are implemented in Julia/JuMP (Dunning et al. 2017) and solved with Gurobi v8.1 (1% optimality gap, 30-minute runtime limit).

¹ https://github.com/s-t-mcdonald/AAM_Corridor_Operations

4.1. Synthetic Instances

Synthetic instances are generated under controlled variations in network size, density, and demand levels to evaluate the scalability of the methodology. Network size is controlled by the number of vertiports (from 5 to 50). Network density is controlled through a *node multiplier*, defined as the ratio of conjunction nodes to vertiports (from 1 to 10). Increasing this parameter raises the number of intermediate routing nodes, and consequently the density of feasible routes in the corridor network. Corridor geometry is further regulated by a minimum angular spacing between corridors sharing a conjunction node (from 0° to 30°) to avoid degenerate configurations. Demand intensity is controlled by the average number of requests originating at each vertiport per hour (from 1 to 10).

For each parameter configuration, we generate three random instances. Vertiport and conjunction locations are sampled uniformly at random on a $100\text{km} \times 100\text{km}$ grid, and each vertiport is connected to its closest conjunction node. Passenger requests are generated by uniformly sampling origin–destination vertiport pairs and request times. Together, these parameters generate instance families that range from small sparse networks to large dense networks with substantial demand.

4.2. Data-driven Instances (New York metropolitan area)

Data-driven instances derive the network topology from FAA corridor infrastructure, calibrate demand from observed commuting flows (U.S. Census data and Google Maps travel times), and model weather disruptions using historical aviation records summarized through a *Weather Severity Index* (WSI). We selected 22 vertiports in the New York metropolitan area based on proximity to cities, population density, and sparsity between vertiports; the resulting locations are shown in Appendix C.

Corridor structures. To capture different levels of airspace organization and infrastructure maturity, we evaluate three alternative corridor networks, ranging from an idealized system with minimal constraints to a realistic network based on existing aviation infrastructure (Figure 5).

- *Direct network.* Vehicles fly directly between any pair of vertiports along straight-line paths. This configuration assumes effectively unconstrained airspace capacity and no predefined corridors or lane restrictions. Provides a baseline representing operational separation in the air rather than tactical separation through routing and dispatching.

- *Grid network.* A structured corridor network is constructed from a 250-mile grid covering the New York region with 20-mile edges. Vertiports are connected to their four closest conjunction nodes. Corridor capacities and multiple lanes are enforced, representing a structured airspace where separation is achieved through routing and dispatching, but without reliance on existing aviation infrastructure.

- *Legacy network.* Corridors follow the Victor airway system currently used for general aviation. Conjunction nodes correspond to navigational aids such as VOR stations, and each vertiport connects to its closest conjunction. This network reflects the likely near-term deployment scenario for AAM operations, leveraging existing corridor infrastructure as envisioned by FAA (2023).

Demand generation. We leverage commuting flows from U.S. Census Bureau (2015) and approximate ground travel times using Google Maps data (Hu et al. 2020). Demand is generated using a discrete-choice model based on relative travel-time savings between self-driving and AAM. For each trip, we randomize the request time within the planning horizon and sample down requests to create different demand levels (e.g., high vs. low demand). This discrete-choice model does not capture demand–supply interactions in the optimization; rather, it reflects that AAM is expected to have a larger traffic share on origin–destination pairs where it provides a comparatively strong level of service, in a pre-processing phase. Appendix C reports supporting visualizations of commuting patterns used in this calibration.

Figure 5 AAM networks in the New York region (vertiports in red, conjunctions in green, corridors in gray).

Weather scenarios. We add weather closures using historical data from aviation ground weather stations (Iowa Environment Mesonet 2023). Each time–space node is closed when the system operates under Instrument Meteorological Conditions at the corresponding location and time. We define the *Weather Severity Index* (WSI) as the percentage of closed nodes over the planning horizon. Appendix C provides visualizations of representative weather scenarios and the distribution of WSI values used in our experiments.

5. Numerical Experiments

This section first examines scalability and then studies the operational implications of the proposed AAM corridor optimization methodology using data-driven experiments calibrated for the New York metropolitan area.

5.1. Scalability Experiments

We evaluate the computational complexity of the AAM corridor problem using synthetic test instances. These controlled experiments compare the AAM problem to a dial-a-ride benchmark and assess the scalability of the proposed flight-based formulation and column generation algorithm on increasingly large instances.

Comparison with Dial-a-Ride. As mentioned earlier, our problem augments a dial-a-ride structure with corridor flow management (capacity constraints in a granular network of corridor conjunctions and vertiports) as well as endogenous flow directionality. These two components add considerable complexity compared to a dial-a-ride benchmark with time windows. This benchmark is obtained by relaxing capacity and directionality constraints (Equations (8)–(10)), which effectively remove capacity restrictions within the corridor network, directionality requirements, and the need for multiple lanes—allowing free-floating routing through the airspace. For an apples-to-apples comparison, both problems are solved using the CBF formulation on the synthetic problem instances.

Figure 6 shows that the AAM problem is significantly more computationally intensive than the dial-a-ride benchmark, with runtimes increasing by up to two orders of magnitude. The complexity of the AAM problem grows further as the number of vertical lanes increases, reflecting the need to coordinate flight trajectories and flow directionality decisions across a capacitated corridor network. These results highlight the structural richness of the AAM corridor problem and motivate the modeling and algorithmic developments proposed in this paper.

Figure 6 Performance of DARP and the AAM problem with varying lane configurations (across 237 instances).

Scalability of the methodology. We evaluate the scalability of the proposed methodology by comparing the flight-based formulation (FBF) with column generation against the corridor-based formulation (CBF) benchmark. For a fair comparison, both approaches are given a one-hour computational budget: 30 minutes for the column generation phase and 30 minutes to solve the resulting integer RMP in FBF, matching the total runtime allowed for CBF. Synthetic instances include up to 50 vertiports, 2,000 corridor conjunctions, and up to 1,000 trip requests. Instances are grouped into “easier” and “harder” (classes 1 and 2, respectively) based on whether an optimality gap of 1% is achieved by any method; instances not solved within a 10% gap are excluded.

Figure 7 illustrates the limited scalability of the CBF benchmark, even on simpler instances (e.g., in the left plot, it achieves the best value in about 60% of cases). This behavior stems from the computational burden of representing flights as sequences of granular arc-level flow decisions across consecutive corridors. In contrast, the FBF formulation embeds these corridor operations directly into flight-level variables, eliminating the need for large sets of flow-conservation constraints. This structural advantage allows FBF to exploit the flexibility of complex corridor networks more effectively, leading to improved tractability and solution quality as instance difficulty increases.

Figure 7 Relative objective values for CBF and FBF (with different initialization schemes).

Initialization strategies. Figure 7 also highlights the importance of initialization strategies in the column generation algorithm. Because column generation focuses on improving the linear relaxation, it may fail to generate routes that are critical for high-quality integer solutions. In particular, the compatible-route initialization provides the best trade-off between runtime and solution quality. The shortest-route initialization often generates a large number of variables, leading to larger optimization models and slower solution times. Nevertheless, when it does produce solutions, they tend to be of (comparatively) high quality. Conversely, the no-initialization approach relies more heavily on column generation and may fail to produce important routes needed for high-quality integer solutions once column generation terminates.

To provide further insight into these results, Table 2 summarizes computational performance. Overall, both the compatible-route and no-initialization approaches yield lower optimality gaps. However, compatible-route initialization tends to produce comparatively better solutions upon completion of the column generation algorithm, while achieving shorter solution times. This approach also attains optimal solutions more frequently on harder instances (see the success rate column), highlighting its robustness in challenging settings.

Table 2 Average computational performance of solution approaches across instance classes.

Class	Approach	Solution Found (%)	Relative Objective	Optimality Gap (%)	Solve Time (s)	CG Solved (%)	Solve Time CG (s)	Success Rate (%)
1	CBF	84.6	1.102	67.4	1,216.6	-	-	63.6
	None	99.8	1.023	2.5	56.1	99.8	42.7	99.6
	SR	97.8	1.002	1.8	116.7	97.6	48.3	97.4
	CR	99.2	1.002	0.6	58.1	99.2	29.7	99.2
2	CBF	42.4	1.492	296.7	3,559.9	-	-	0.0
	None	98.8	1.024	6.2	783.7	98.3	198.0	72.6
	SR	81.0	1.066	22.7	1,114.7	78.6	258.0	58.8
	CR	91.0	1.004	7.9	563.3	90.5	157.7	82.8

FBF initialization schemes: “SR” (shortest-route), “CR” (compatible-route), and “None” (no initial routes).

The FBF optimality gap relies on a lower bound computed with the most recent reduced cost as $r_c |\mathcal{T}| |\mathcal{V}|$.

Optimality gaps and solution times are averaged across instances where an integer feasible solution is obtained.

“Success rate” denotes the fraction of instances solved within 1% optimality (for FBF, column generation must also converge).

Backward pricing. Further improvements arise from the backward pricing algorithm introduced in Section 3.3. Table 3 compares the forward and backward pricing approaches across network size and density. The backward algorithm consistently reduces solution times, achieving speedups of approximately 50–60% on large instances. These improvements stem from the reduction in the number of shortest-path computations required during pricing.

Overall, these results demonstrate the scalability of the formulation and column generation algorithm, and highlight the benefits of the proposed acceleration strategies, including initialization and pricing. Instances involving up to 50 vertiports, 2,000 corridor conjunctions, and 1,000 trip requests can be solved within practical computational limits, whereas the arc-based benchmark struggles to scale beyond small networks. Next, we evaluate the operational performance of the methodology on data-driven instances.

5.2. Data-Driven Experiments for the New York Metropolitan Area

We evaluate the operational implications of the proposed methodology on data-driven instances calibrated for the New York metropolitan area. These experiments quantify the benefits of integrated corridor optimization and examine the main drivers of system performance. We first assess the value

Table 3 Solution time in seconds (five random seeds, demand multiplier of 10, one-hour horizon).

Initialization	PP algorithm	V = 5		V = 10		V = 25		V = 50	
		NM=2	NM=10	NM=2	NM=10	NM=2	NM=10	NM=2	NM=10
None	Forward	4.55	25.37	15.14	62.43	238.94	655.29	5631.07	4357.55
	Backward	5.53	23.11	14.31	39.79	100.32	179.46	2363.19	2082.95
SR	Forward	3.88	12.07	23.87	86.73	1157.31	898.02	6400.53	4734.94
	Backward	3.84	11.3	18.39	48.64	385.47	455.22	3897.01	3569.04
CR	Forward	4.95	15.49	14.33	18.44	255.5	148.12	2476.7	1201.64
	Backward	4.71	12.46	11.67	15.58	96.38	92.33	969.51	593.05

“SR”: shortest-route initialization; “CR”: compatible-route initialization; “NM”: node multiplier.

of integrated optimization, dynamic flow directionality, and column generation. We then identify the main operational bottlenecks through the effects of corridor constraints, network structure, and weather disruptions, and finally examine resulting corridor utilization patterns and their implications for the design of emerging AAM systems.

Benefits of the proposed methodology

Integrated optimization. Table 4 shows that ignoring key structural elements of corridor-based AAM operations leads to substantial losses in both profit and demand coverage. In particular, ignoring corridor flow directionality alone results in a 10–20% loss in profit and demand coverage. When corridor conjunction capacities are also ignored, the loss increases to roughly 15–25%. To obtain these benchmarks, we determine dispatching, routing, and passenger service decisions under the simplified models and then re-optimize operations within the full operational framework. The first benchmark ignores directionality, the second further removes corridor capacities at conjunction nodes (corresponding to a capacitated dial-a-ride problem), and the last benchmarks additionally eliminate takeoff/landing and parking capacities at vertiports, with the final benchmark corresponding to an uncapacitated dial-a-ride formulation. Although lifting vertiport capacities partially restores profit by enabling additional flights, these simplified models still incur an average loss of about 15% relative to the integrated optimization methodology.

Table 4 Relative loss (%) of lifting key structural constraints (cumulatively, from left to right).

Lanes per corridor	Vehicles per vertiport	Corridor directions (10)		Corridor conjunctions (8)		Takeoff/landing capacity (6)		Parking capacity (7)	
		Profit loss	Demand loss	Profit loss	Demand loss	Profit loss	Demand loss	Profit loss	Demand loss
2	3	-17.3%	-19.3%	-25.8%	-28.2%	-18.2%	-21.9%	-17.3%	-21.5%
	10	-10.6%	-13.0%	-26.5%	-30.7%	-16.6%	-23.2%	-15.3%	-21.7%
4	3	-16.2%	-18.4%	-19.2%	-21.9%	-15.3%	-19.9%	-14.2%	-19.3%
	10	-12.4%	-15.8%	-22.3%	-26.8%	-14.7%	-21.3%	-15.1%	-21.5%
8	3	-11.4%	-12.8%	-13.7%	-15.5%	-12.1%	-16.5%	-10.7%	-14.7%
	10	-9.9%	-12.7%	-15.3%	-19.7%	-13.0%	-19.8%	-13.3%	-19.6%

Dynamic flow directionality. Figure 8 shows that allowing corridor-lane directionality to dynamically change over time substantially improves both profit and demand coverage. Direction changes occur in roughly 5–15% of time periods and yield improvements of 10–60%, with larger gains when the demand-to-supply ratio is high. These results suggest that operating flexibility becomes most valuable when the AAM system operates close to capacity.

Figure 8 Benefit of optimization versus static flow directions in each corridor-lane.

Column generation. Figure 9 shows that column generation improves solutions relative to a standalone compatible-route heuristic, in which the integer RMP contains only the initialization columns. Under intermediate weather conditions, column generation identifies alternative trajectories that avoid weather disruptions and inter-flight conflicts, generating up to 5% of active flights and producing profit improvements of up to 23%, with trajectory deviations reaching up to 50% relative to shortest paths.

Figure 9 Benefits of column generation (CG) versus compatible-route heuristic, as a function of WSI.

Drivers of system performance

Operational constraints. To identify the drivers of AAM operating performance in more detail, we start from an unconstrained system with infinite capacity and a direct network structure, and progressively add: vertiport capacities, the corridor structure in the legacy network, corridor capacities from horizontal separations, and historical weather conditions. Figure 10 reports the percent-wise loss of profit relative to the unconstrained system as increasingly realistic operational constraints are introduced. At the structural level, the results highlight the dominant impact of the corridor network and adverse weather on AAM operations. Vertiport takeoff/landing and parking capacities act as relatively mild bottlenecks, leading to a profit loss of about 5%. In contrast, introducing the legacy corridor network results in a much larger loss of 30–40%, while introducing horizontal separation requirements only induces an additional loss of roughly 7%. Finally, adverse weather conditions further reduce profit by approximately 15%. At a finer level of operational detail, the magnitude of these effects varies with system parameters such as the number of vertical lanes, vehicle fleet size, and turnaround times. In particular, corridor capacities and weather disruptions have a stronger impact in denser operating regimes induced by fewer lanes, shorter turnaround times, and larger fleets. On the other hand, the impact of vertiport capacities is also amplified as the fleet size increases, and mitigated when fewer lanes relax pressure on landing and takeoff throughput, or when faster turnaround times reduce parking congestion. Altogether, these results highlight vertiport operations, horizontal separations, and vertical separations as key levers that AAM operators can adjust to improve system throughput.

Figure 10 Performance of AAM with progressively added constraints relative to the unconstrained system.

Corridor network structure. Figure 11 further isolates the role of corridor structure. Echoing Figure 10, the legacy network induces a significant profit loss of 20–40% relative to the uncapacitated direct network. This loss is larger with fewer lanes, longer turnaround times, and smaller fleets, all reflecting tighter supply constraints. For similar reasons, the grid network also performs worse than the direct network when the number of vertical lanes is small. However, with more lanes, the grid network tends to outperform the direct network because corridor capacity restrictions become less binding while vehicles gain additional routing flexibility to circumvent bottlenecks at vertiports. For instance, it may be optimal for a vehicle to take a detour when the arrival vertiport operates at capacity—akin to ATFM interventions in legacy air transportation systems.

Figure 11 Percent-wise profit change in the grid and legacy networks relative to the direct network.

Weather disruptions. Figure 12 isolates the impact of adverse weather on system performance. For instance, a 25% incidence of poor weather leads to a profit loss greater than 50%, while a 50% WSI leads to a loss of roughly 75%. The primary mechanism is a revenue loss due to a smaller demand coverage, and the secondary mechanism involves a cost increase due to spatial detours to avoid adverse weather. Using the historical WSI distribution, AAM operators should expect an average profit loss of about 24%, with a long tail reaching up to 80–100%. These findings further highlight the critical impact of weather-related closures on the profitability and reliability of AAM operations.

Figure 12 Effects of weather on operating profit.

Corridor utilization patterns. An illustrative visualization of AAM traffic patterns is provided in Appendix D (Figure 19). At the aggregate level, Figure 13 highlights the spatial heterogeneity of corridor usage. For instance, the corridors from Long Island through New Jersey to Allentown, PA carry more than 10% of flights, whereas most corridors handle between 1% and 6% of traffic. In

other words, the bottlenecks of AAM operations may be highly concentrated locally in the network. This echoes the guidelines from FAA (2023) to increase capacity in high-traffic corridors, via infrastructure investments (e.g., to expand vertical lanes or the corridor topology) or via operational enhancements (e.g., to safely reduce separation requirements or operate under adverse weather). Direction changes are also unevenly distributed across the network. Low traffic corridors rarely change direction due to excess capacity, while highly congested corridors also exhibit few changes because temporary idleness can offset the benefits of switching directions. In contrast, direction changes are most beneficial on corridors that have some excess capacity (to absorb idleness) and relatively high demand (to benefit from the new direction).

Figure 13 Heatmap of corridor traffic and directionality changes across instances and parameters.

Policy implications. These results have important implications for the design of emerging AAM systems. While much attention has focused on vertiport design to maximize takeoff/landing and parking capacities (see, e.g. Vascik and Hansman 2019, Schweiger and Preis 2022, McKinsey & Co. 2020), our results highlight the importance of en-route bottlenecks. Legacy corridor structures reduce demand coverage and operating profit, and weather-related closures further exacerbate these losses. These findings suggest that AAM operators and policymakers should account for corridor network structures and weather disruptions in financial projections and infrastructure planning.

6. Conclusion

Advanced Air Mobility (AAM) offers new opportunities for efficient and sustainable transport, but requires decision tools to manage on-demand operations in high-density corridor networks. This paper developed a scalable integer optimization methodology for AAM operations that integrates vehicle dispatching and routing decisions with trajectory planning in a granular capacitated corridor network. The formulation combines elements of dial-a-ride models with time windows and flow-management models, while endogenizing corridor-lane directionality. The problem is solved using a column generation framework with a backward label-setting pricing algorithm that exploits the structure of the trajectory subproblem.

Using both synthetic and real-world data, the proposed methodology scales to realistic networks with up to 50 vertiports and 2,000 corridor conjunctions, while improving profit and demand coverage by up to 15% relative to benchmarks. The results highlight the value of jointly optimizing modular trajectories and corridor directionality in capacitated AAM networks, and identify the

impact of corridor constraints and weather disruptions on system performance. Overall, this work provides one of the first integrated optimization approaches to on-demand AAM operations in corridor networks and offers insights to guide the design and operation of emerging AAM systems.

References

- Agarwal R, Ergun Ö (2008) Ship scheduling and network design for cargo routing in liner shipping. *Transportation Science* 42(2):175–196.
- AIAA Certification Task Force (2025) Challenges to the commercialization of advanced air mobility vehicles. Technical report, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), URL <https://aiaa.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/1aiaa-challenges-to-the-commercialization-of-aam-digital.pdf>.
- Airbus (2018) UTM Blueprint for the Skies.
- Ale-Ahmad H, Mahmassani HS (2021) Capacitated location-allocation-routing problem with time windows for on-demand urban air taxi operation. *Transportation Research Record* 2675(10):1092–1114.
- Alyasiry AM, Forbes M, Bulmer M (2019) An exact algorithm for the pickup and delivery problem with time windows and last-in-first-out loading. *Transportation Science* 53(6):1695–1705.
- Ball M, Hoffman R, Odoni A, Rifkin R (2003) A Stochastic Integer Program with Dual Network Structure and its Application to the Ground-Holding Problem. *Operations Research* 51(1):167–171.
- Barnhart C, Bertsimas D, Caramanis C, Fearing D (2012) Equitable and Efficient Coordination in Traffic Flow Management. *Transportation Science* 46(2):262–280.
- Bertsimas D, Frankovich M, Odoni A (2011a) Optimal selection of airport runway configurations. *Operations research* 59(6):1407–1419.
- Bertsimas D, Gupta S (2016) Fairness and Collaboration in Network Air Traffic Flow Management: An Optimization Approach. *Transportation Science* 50(1):57–76.
- Bertsimas D, Lulli G, Odoni A (2011b) An Integer Optimization Approach to Large-Scale Air Traffic Flow Management. *Operations Research* 59(1):211–227.
- Bertsimas D, Stock Patterson S (1998) The Air Traffic Flow Management Problem with Enroute Capacities. *Operations Research* 46(3):406–422.
- Bharadwaj S, Wongpiromsarn T, Neogi N, Muffoletto J, Topcu U (2021) Minimum-violation traffic management for urban air mobility. *NASA Formal Methods: 13th International Symposium, NFM 2021, Virtual Event, May 24–28, 2021, Proceedings*, 37–52 (Springer).
- Binder R, Garrow LA, German B, Mokhtarian P, Daskilewicz M, Douthat TH (2018) If you fly it, will commuters come? a survey to model demand for evtol urban air trips. *2018 Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference*, 2882.
- Birolini S, Jacquillat A (2023) Day-ahead aircraft routing with data-driven primary delay predictions. *European Journal of Operational Research* in press.
- Boland N, Hewitt M, Marshall L, Savelsbergh M (2017) The continuous-time service network design problem. *Operations Research* 65(5):1303–1321.
- Booz Allen Hamilton (2018) Urban Air Mobility (UAM) Market Study. Technical report, National Aeronautics and Space Administration.
- Bosson C, Lauderdale TA (2018) Simulation evaluations of an autonomous urban air mobility network management and separation service. *2018 Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference*, 3365.
- Brown A, Harris W (2018) A vehicle design and optimization model for on-demand aviation. *2018 AIAA/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference*, 0105.
- Brunelli M, Ditta CC, Postorino MN (2023) New infrastructures for urban air mobility systems: A systematic review on vertiport location and capacity. *Journal of Air Transport Management* 112:102460.

- Chin C, Gopalakrishnan K, Balakrishnan H, Egorov M, Evans A (2021) Efficient and fair traffic flow management for on-demand air mobility. *CEAS Aeronautical Journal* 1–11.
- Chin C, Gopalakrishnan K, Balakrishnan H, Egorov M, Evans A (2023) Protocol-based congestion management for advanced air mobility. *Journal of Air Transportation* 31(1):35–44.
- Cordeau JF (2006) A branch-and-cut algorithm for the dial-a-ride problem. *Operations Research* 54(3):573–586.
- Crainic TG, Hewitt M, Toulouse M, Vu DM (2016) Service network design with resource constraints. *Transportation Science* 50(4):1380–1393.
- Dabia S, Ropke S, Van Woensel T, De Kok T (2013) Branch and price for the time-dependent vehicle routing problem with time windows. *Transportation science* 47(3):380–396.
- Daskilewicz M, German B, Warren M, Garrow LA, Boddupalli SS, Douthat TH (2018) Progress in vertiport placement and estimating aircraft range requirements for evtol daily commuting. *2018 Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference*, 2884.
- Dogan M, Jacquillat A (2025) On-demand service sharing via collective dynamic pricing. *Working paper* .
- Dunning I, Huchette J, Lubin M (2017) Jump: A modeling language for mathematical optimization. *SIAM review* 59(2):295–320.
- Espinoza D, Garcia R, Goycoolea M, Nemhauser GL, Savelsbergh MW (2008a) Per-seat, on-demand air transportation part i: Problem description and an integer multicommodity flow model. *Transportation Science* 42(3):263–278.
- Espinoza D, Garcia R, Goycoolea M, Nemhauser GL, Savelsbergh MW (2008b) Per-seat, on-demand air transportation part ii: Parallel local search. *Transportation Science* 42(3):279–291.
- FAA (2023) Concept of Operations for Urban Air Mobility (UAM) (ConOps 2.0).
- Fleischmann B, Gietz M, Gnutzmann S (2004) Time-varying travel times in vehicle routing. *Transportation science* 38(2):160–173.
- Florio AM, Absi N, Feillet D (2021) Routing electric vehicles on congested street networks. *Transportation Science* 55(1):238–256.
- Garrow LA, German B, Mokhtarian P, Glodek J (2019) A survey to model demand for evtol urban air trips and competition with autonomous ground vehicles. *AIAA Aviation 2019 Forum*, 2871.
- Garrow LA, Mokhtarian P, German B, Boddupalli SS (2020) Commuting in the age of the jetsons: a market segmentation analysis of autonomous ground vehicles and air taxis in five large us cities. *AIAA Aviation 2020 Forum*, 3258.
- Goodrich KH, Theodore CR (2021) Description of the NASA urban air mobility maturity level (UML) scale. *AIAA Scitech 2021 Forum* (American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics), ISBN 978-1-62410-609-5, URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.2514/6.2021-1627>.
- Ha TH, Lee K, Hwang JT (2019) Large-scale design-economics optimization of evtol concepts for urban air mobility. *AIAA Scitech 2019 Forum*, 1218.
- Hu Y, Wang C, Li R, Wang F (2020) Estimating a large drive time matrix between zip codes in the united states: a differential sampling approach. *Journal of transport geography* 86:102770.
- Hua, Wang, Yu, Zhu, Wang (2019) Control Strategy Optimization for Two-Lane Highway Lane-Closure Work Zones. *Sustainability* 11(17):4567, ISSN 2071-1050, URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su11174567>.
- Iowa Environment Mesonet (2023) Available at: <https://mesonet.agron.iastate.edu>.
- Jacquillat A (2022) Predictive and prescriptive analytics toward passenger-centric ground delay programs. *Transportation Science* 56(2):265–298.
- Jacquillat A, Odoni AR, Webster MD (2017) Dynamic control of runway configurations and of arrival and departure service rates at JFK airport under stochastic queue conditions. *Transportation Science* 51(1):155–176.
- Jiang Y, Li Z, Wang Y, Xue Q (2025) Vertiport location for evtol considering multidimensional demand of urban air mobility: An application in beijing. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice* 192:104353.
- Kleinbekman IC, Mitici M, Wei P (2020) Rolling-horizon electric vertical takeoff and landing arrival scheduling for on-demand urban air mobility. *Journal of Aerospace Information Systems* 17(3):150–159.

- Ko J, Ahn J (2025) On-demand urban air mobility scheduling with operational considerations. *Journal of Aerospace Information Systems* 22(5):401–411.
- Kotwicz Herniczek MT, Yılmaz E, Sanni O, German BJ (2022) Drawing the highways in the sky for urban air mobility operations. *Journal of Air Transportation* 30(4):170–181.
- Lee J, Marla L, Jacquillat A (2020) Dynamic disruption management in airline networks under airport operating uncertainty. *Transportation Science* 54(4):973–997.
- Li S, Egorov M, Kochenderfer MJ (2020) Analysis of fleet management and infrastructure constraints in on-demand urban air mobility operations. *AIAA Aviation 2020 Forum*, 2907.
- Liebchen C (2008) The first optimized railway timetable in practice. *Transportation Science* 42(4):420–435.
- Liu Y, Pan T, Tan J, Zhong R, Chen C (2026) Integrated take-off management and trajectory optimization for merging control in urban air mobility corridors. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 182:105370.
- Liu Y, Yu Y, Zhang Y, Baldacci R, Tang J, Luo X, Sun W (2023) Branch-cut-and-price for the time-dependent green vehicle routing problem with time windows. *INFORMS Journal on Computing* 35(1):14–30.
- Lu Y, Zeng W, Wei W, Wu W, Jiang H (2025) Urban air mobility vertiports: A bibliometric analysis of applications, challenges, and emerging directions. *Applied Sciences* 15(20):10961.
- Lübbecke E, Lübbecke ME, Möhring RH (2019) Ship traffic optimization for the Kiel Canal. *Operations Research* 67(3):791–812.
- Martin-Iradi B, Schmid A, Cummings K, Jacquillat A (2024) A double decomposition algorithm for network planning and operations in deviated fixed-route microtransit. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.01265*.
- McKinsey & Co (2020) To take off, flying vehicles first need places to land. Technical report.
- McKinsey & Co (2022) Perspectives on advanced air mobility; Navigating the emerging passenger urban and regional air-mobility industry. Technical report.
- Mueller ER, Kopardekar PH, Goodrich KH (2017) Enabling airspace integration for high-density on-demand mobility operations. *17th AIAA Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference*, 3086.
- NASA (2020) UAM Vision Concept of Operations (ConOps) UAM Maturity Level (UML) 4.
- Odoni A (1987) The Flow Management Problem in Air Traffic Control. Odoni A, Bianco L, Szego G, eds., *Flow Control of Congested Networks* (Springer-Verlag).
- Patterson MD, German BJ, Moore MD (2012) Performance analysis and design of on-demand electric aircraft concepts. *12th AIAA Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations (ATIO) Conference and 14th AIAA/ISSMO Multidisciplinary Analysis and Optimization Conference*.
- Pradeep P, Wei P (2018) Heuristic approach for arrival sequencing and scheduling for evtol aircraft in on-demand urban air mobility. *2018 IEEE/AIAA 37th Digital Avionics Systems Conference (DASC)*, 1–7 (IEEE).
- Qu Y, Bard JF (2015) A branch-and-price-and-cut algorithm for heterogeneous pickup and delivery problems with configurable vehicle capacity. *Transportation Science* 49(2):254–270.
- Rajendran S, Zack J (2019) Insights on strategic air taxi network infrastructure locations using an iterative constrained clustering approach. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 128:470–505.
- Rath S, Chow JY (2022) Air taxi skyport location problem with single-allocation choice-constrained elastic demand for airport access. *Journal of Air Transport Management* 105:102294.
- Richetta O, Odoni A (1993) Solving Optimally the Static Ground-Holding Policy Problem in Air Traffic Control. *Transportation Science* 27(3):228–237.
- Righini G, Salani M (2006) Symmetry helps: Bounded bi-directional dynamic programming for the elementary shortest path problem with resource constraints. *Discrete Optimization* 3(3):255–273.
- Schweiger K, Preis L (2022) Urban air mobility: Systematic review of scientific publications and regulations for vertiport design and operations. *Drones* 6(7), ISSN 2504-446X, URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/drones6070179>.
- Shihab SAM, Wei P, Ramirez DSJ, Mesa-Arango R, Bloebaum C (2019) By schedule or on demand?-a hybrid operation concept for urban air mobility. *AIAA Aviation 2019 Forum*, 3522.

- Sun L, Wei P, Xie W (2023) Fair and risk-averse urban air mobility resource allocation under uncertainties. *Available at SSRN 4343979*.
- Terrab M, Odoni A (1993) Strategic Flow Management for Air Traffic Control. *Operations Research* 41(1):138–152.
- Thippavong DP, Apaza R, Barmore B, Battiste V, Burian B, Dao Q, Feary M, Go S, Goodrich KH, Homola J, et al. (2018) Urban air mobility airspace integration concepts and considerations. *2018 Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference*, 3676.
- US Census Bureau (2015) Commuting flows. Available at: <https://www.census.gov/topics/employment/commuting>.
- Vascik PD, Hansman RJ (2017) Evaluation of key operational constraints affecting on-demand mobility for aviation in the los angeles basin: ground infrastructure, air traffic control and noise. *17th AIAA Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference*, 3084.
- Vascik PD, Hansman RJ (2019) Development of vertiport capacity envelopes and analysis of their sensitivity to topological and operational factors. *AIAA Scitech 2019 Forum*, 0526.
- Vertical Flight Society (2023) eVTOL Aircraft Directory. Technical report.
- Volakakis V, Mahmassani HS (2024) Vertiport infrastructure location optimization for equitable access to urban air mobility. *Infrastructures* 9(12):239.
- Vossen T, Ball M (2006) Slot Trading Opportunities in Collaborative Ground Delay Programs. *Transportation Science* 40(1):29–43.
- Vranas P, Bertsimas D, Odoni A (1994) The Multi-airport Ground-holding Problem in Air Traffic Control. *Operations Research* 42(2):249–261.
- Wang K, Jacquillat A, Vaze V (2022a) Vertiport planning for urban aerial mobility: An adaptive discretization approach. *Manufacturing & Service Operations Management* 24(6):3215–3235.
- Wang Z, Delahaye D, Farges JL, Alam S (2022b) Complexity optimal air traffic assignment in multi-layer transport network for urban air mobility operations. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 142:103776.
- White House (2023) National aeronautics science and technology priorities.
- Willey LC, Salmon JL (2021) A method for urban air mobility network design using hub location and subgraph isomorphism. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 125:102997.
- Wu Z, Zhang Y (2021) Integrated network design and demand forecast for on-demand urban air mobility. *Engineering* 7(4):473–487.
- Zhang W, Jacquillat A, Wang K, Wang S (2023) Routing optimization with vehicle–customer coordination. *Management Science* 69(11):6876–6897.
- Zhang Y, Lu M, Shen S (2021) On the values of vehicle-to-grid electricity selling in electric vehicle sharing. *Manufacturing & Service Operations Management* 23(2):488–507.
- Zhao Y, Hu Y, Feng T, Zhang A (2025) Passengers’ vertiport choices for integrated urban air mobility and airline services. *Transport Policy*.
- Zinder Y, Lazarev AA, Musatova EG, Tarasov IA (2018) Scheduling the two-way traffic on a single-track railway with a siding. *Automation and Remote Control* 79:506–523.

Appendix A: Details from Section 2

CBF benchmark: corridor-based flow formulation The corridor-based flow (CBF) formulation models vehicle operations at a granular level: vehicles depart, traverse, and arrive along arcs of the time–space–lane network. Compared with the flight-based flow (FBF) formulation, flow conservation constraints explicitly enforce four-dimensional continuity across nodes.

To maintain consistency between passenger service decisions and resulting flight trajectories, the binary arc variables (E, W) are augmented with a destination index j . Thus, E_{cjl}^t and W_{cjl}^t indicate whether a vehicle flies eastward or westward in corridor c toward vertiport j in lane ℓ at time t (see Figure 14). The resulting CBF model is expressed as follows:

$$\min \sum_{n \in \mathcal{P}} \pi_n R_n + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} \left(h_\ell A_{j\ell}^t + \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} d_c (E_{cjl}^t + W_{cjl}^t) \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{c \in \delta_e^-(i)} E_{cjl}^t + \sum_{c \in \delta_w^-(i)} W_{cjl}^t = D_{ij\ell}^t, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, j \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{i\}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{c \in \delta_e^+(j)} E_{cjl}^{t-\Delta_c} + \sum_{c \in \delta_w^+(j)} W_{cjl}^{t-\Delta_c} = A_{j\ell}^t, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{V}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{c \in \delta_e^-(i)} (E_{cjl}^{t-\Delta_c} - W_{cjl}^t) + \sum_{c \in \delta_w^+(i)} (W_{cjl}^{t-\Delta_c} - E_{cjl}^t) = 0, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{V}, j \in \mathcal{V}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} A_{i\ell}^{t-\tau} + I_i^{t-1} - I_i^t - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} D_{ij\ell}^t = 0, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} A_{i\ell}^t + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} D_{ij\ell}^t \leq \Gamma_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (21)$$

$$I_i^t + \sum_{s=0}^{\tau-1} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} A_{i\ell}^{t-s} \leq \Omega_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22)$$

$$\sum_{c \in \delta_e^-(i)} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} E_{cjl}^t + \sum_{c \in \delta_w^-(i)} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} W_{cjl}^t \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} E_{cjl}^t \leq e_{c\ell}^{\lfloor t/\Delta_c \rfloor}, \quad \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} W_{cjl}^t \leq w_{c\ell}^{\lfloor t/\Delta_c \rfloor}, \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (24)$$

$$e_{c\ell}^{s+u} + w_{c\ell}^s \leq 1, \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \ell \in \mathcal{L}, s \in \{0, 1, \dots, \lceil |\mathcal{T}|/\Delta_c \rceil\}, u \in \{-1, 0, 1\} \quad (25)$$

$$R_n + \sum_{k=0}^{M_n} T_{nk} = 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{P} \quad (26)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{P}} \sum_{k=0}^{M_n} \mathbf{1}(n \in \mathcal{P}_{ij}^{t-k}) T_{nk} \leq \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} D_{ij\ell}^t, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{V} | i \neq j, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (27)$$

$$I_i^0 = \Psi_i \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V} \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{T} \text{ binary, } \mathbf{I} \text{ integer} \quad (29)$$

The objective function (16) optimizes operating profit by minimizing revenue losses from rejected demand and costs associated with four-dimensional vehicle trajectories. Constraints (17)–(19) enforce flow conservation at departure and arrival vertiports and across corridor conjunctions, thereby defining feasible four-dimensional trajectories through the corridor network. Constraint (20) maintains ground flow conservation at each vertiport, equating total incoming idle and arrival flows to outgoing idle and departure flows. Throughput limits on takeoffs and landings are imposed by Constraint (21), while parking capacities on idle and inbound vehicles are enforced by Constraint (22). The unit-capacity restriction in each conjunction–lane (Constraint (23)) ensures horizontal separation in the discretized time–space network. Constraints (24) couple vehicle flows with corridor directionality decisions, and Constraint (25) enforces uni-directionality and a one-period changeover time when lanes reverse direction. Passenger service logic is defined by Constraints (26)–(27), which ensure that each request is either rejected or accepted with a feasible delay, while

also allowing repositioning of idle vehicles when availability at other vertiports is insufficient. Finally, Constraint (28) initializes the network state, and Constraint (29) specifies variable domains.

Figure 14 Flow propagation in the CBF formulation through the time–space network (eastward down, westward up).

Proof of Proposition 1 Let $\Delta_r^f \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ denote the number of time units required to traverse route $r \in \mathcal{R}$ in formulation $f \in \{\text{CBF}, \text{FBF}\}$; let $\Delta_r^* \in \mathbb{R}_+$ denote the corresponding travel time without time discretization. The time fidelity metric $\Psi^f(\kappa)$ measures the largest absolute error between the actual and estimated travel times, with a time discretization of κ units:

$$\Psi^f(\kappa) = \max_{r \in \mathcal{R}} |\Delta_r^f - \Delta_r^*| \kappa.$$

Using this metric, we show that the CBF formulation can have arbitrarily large errors by accumulating rounding errors from corridor to corridor along possibly long trajectories.

Suppose by contradiction that there exists an upper bound $\mu(\kappa)$ on $\Psi^{\text{CBF}}(\kappa)$ for any given network. Define r to be a route that traverses $2\lceil\mu(\kappa)\rceil + 2$ corridors from the origin vertiport to the destination vertiport, where each corridor takes 0.5 time units to traverse. In the CBF formulation, the travel time in each corridor $c \in \mathcal{C}$ will be assigned a value $\Delta_c \geq 1$, so that $\Delta_r^{\text{CBF}} = \sum_{i=1}^{2\lceil\mu(\kappa)\rceil+2} \Delta_c \geq 2\lceil\mu(\kappa)\rceil + 2$. However, in reality, the travel time is given by $\Delta_r^* = \lceil\mu(\kappa)\rceil + 1$. This yields $|\Delta_r^{\text{CBF}} - \Delta_r^*| \geq \lceil\mu(\kappa)\rceil + 1 > \mu(\kappa)$, contradicting the fact that $\mu(\kappa)$ is an upper bound of the error.

Now we focus on the FBF formulation. By definition, for any route $r \in \mathcal{A}_j$, we have $\Delta_r^* = (\sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r,j)} d_c)/v$ and $\Delta_r^{\text{FBF}} = \Phi(r, j) = \lceil(\sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r,j)} d_c)/v\rceil$. This directly yields that $|\Delta_r^{\text{FBF}} - \Delta_r^*| \leq 1$, hence $\Psi^{\text{FBF}}(\kappa) \leq \kappa$.

Proof of Proposition 2 First note that variables $E_{c_j\ell}^t$ and $W_{c_j\ell}^t$ in CBF can be equivalently defined as non-negative integers (instead of binary) because they are already bounded by one through Constraint (23). The FBF formulation is obtained by eliminating Constraint (19) (flow conservation at conjunction nodes). Thus, the feasible set of the Dantzig–Wolfe (DW) subproblem becomes

$$\mathcal{F} = \{E_{c_j\ell}^t, W_{c_j\ell}^t \in \mathbb{Z}_+ : \sum_{c \in \delta_i^+(i)} (E_{c_j\ell}^{t-\Delta_c} - W_{c_j\ell}^t) + \sum_{c \in \delta_w^-(i)} (W_{c_j\ell}^{t-\Delta_c} - E_{c_j\ell}^t) = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{V}, \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T}\},$$

and we note that $\text{conv}(\mathcal{F})$ is a cone.

Let \mathcal{P} denote the linear relaxation of \mathcal{F} . It can be verified that $\mathcal{P} = \text{conv}(\mathcal{F})$: \mathcal{F} has a flow conservation structure (without sink or source nodes), and as such it corresponds to an ideal formulation. Therefore, $\text{conv}(\mathcal{F})$ can be expressed as all conic combinations of a set of extreme rays of \mathcal{P} . The flight-based variables $F_{r\ell}^t$ represent such extreme rays, where any conic combination of them constitutes a feasible flow in the sense of \mathcal{P} .

It remains to argue that the extreme rays $F_{r\ell}^t$ correspond to flights. This follows from the flow conservation structure of Constraint (19), which applies only at conjunction nodes (and not at vertiports). Hence, any unit flow routed along a time-consistent path between two vertiports (departing at a given time and using a specific lane) yields a feasible element of \mathcal{F} . Any solution that routes flow along multiple paths can be expressed as a conic combination of single-path flows. This establishes that the FBF formulation defines a DW reformulation of the CBF formulation.

Appendix B: Details from Section 3

Forward Label-setting Algorithm The Bellman-Ford algorithm finds the shortest path between one source node and all other nodes. Due to the dependency of the arc weights on the arrival vertiport in TSLN- j , we can only retrieve the shortest path from one departure vertiport to one arrival vertiport at a time (Figure 4a). The forward algorithm therefore loops over all vertiport pairs and solves $O(|\mathcal{V}|^2)$ shortest-path problems, as detailed in Algorithm 3 and Proposition 5.

Algorithm 3 Forward-pair label-setting algorithm

```

for  $i \in \mathcal{V}$ ,  $j \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{i\}$  do
  Run the Bellman–Ford algorithm to find the shortest path in TSLN- $j$  from  $M_i$  to  $M_j$   $\triangleright |\mathcal{V}|^2$  times
  Find the corresponding route  $r \in \mathcal{R}$ ,  $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ , and  $t \in \mathcal{T}$ , and the corresponding reduced cost
  If the reduced cost is negative, add the  $(r, \ell, t)$  uplet to the set  $\mathcal{S}$ 
end for

```

Proof of Proposition 3. This is a direct consequence of Proposition 2, which states that FBF arises from a Dantzig–Wolfe reformulation. As such, finite convergence is guaranteed, provided that the pricing problem is solved exactly.

Proof of Proposition 4. Let p be a path between from M_i to M_j in TSLN- j . Let us define a unique flight-based variable $F_{r\ell}^t$. Since the first node of p is M_i , there exists a departure time $t \in \mathcal{T}$ and a lane $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ such that the second node of the path is $N_{i\ell}^t$, by construction of TSLN- j . Moreover, there exists an arrival time $k \in \mathcal{T}$ such that the second-to-last node of the path will be $N_{j\ell}^k$, again by construction of TSLN- j . All the arcs between $N_{i\ell}^t$ and $N_{j\ell}^k$ define a sequence of corridors $c_1, \dots, c_v \in \mathcal{C}$. By construction, this sequence corresponds to a route $r \in \mathcal{R}$, because the sequence of corridors satisfies flow balance constraints and because the route terminates at time $k < |\mathcal{T}|$. Since route r begins at vertiport i and terminates at vertiport j , we have $r \in \mathcal{D}_{ij}$, so path p corresponds to a unique $t \in \mathcal{T}$, $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ and $r \in \mathcal{D}_{ij} \subset \mathcal{R}$.

The sum of the edge weights on the path can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sum of Edge Weights on Path } p = \gamma_{ij\ell}^t \text{ (Departure arc)} \\
& + \kappa_{j\ell}^{t+\sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r,j)} \Delta_c} \text{ (Arrival arc)} \\
& + \sum_{u=1}^v 1_e(r, c_u) \psi_{c_u\ell}^{t+\sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r, \zeta_{c_u}^w)} \Delta_c} \text{ (En-route east flow arcs)} \\
& + \sum_{u=1}^v 1_w(r, c_u) \xi_{c_u\ell}^{t+\sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r, \zeta_{c_u}^e)} \Delta_c} \text{ (En-route east flow arcs)} \\
& = \gamma_{ij\ell}^t + \kappa_{j\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,j)} + \sum_{c \in \mathcal{E}_r} \psi_{c\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_c^w)} + \sum_{c \in \mathcal{W}_r} \xi_{c\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_c^e)},
\end{aligned}$$

where we use the facts that $\Phi(r, j) = \sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r,j)} \Delta_c$ by assumption, and that $\sum_{u=1}^v 1_e(r, c) \psi_{c\ell}^{t+\sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r, \zeta_c^w)} \Delta_c} = \sum_{c \in \mathcal{E}_r} \psi_{c\ell}^{t+\sum_{c \in \mathcal{K}(r, \zeta_c^w)} \Delta_c}$ (with a similar equality for the west flow direction). We can recognize the reduced cost of the flight-based variable $F_{r\ell}^t$ in the FBF formulation.

Vice versa, we can use the same principles to transform any flight-based variable $F_{r\ell}^t$, for $t \in \mathcal{T}$, $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ and $r \in \mathcal{D}_{ij} \subset \mathcal{R}$, into path in TSLN- j . By construction of TSLN- j , there exists an arc from M_i to node $N_{i\ell}^t$ with edge weight $\gamma_{ij\ell}^t$. The route r then traverses a sequence of corridors c_1, \dots, c_v . Thus, there exists an arc from $N_{i\ell}^t$ to $N_{i\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,i)}$ if the route first travels in the east direction (to $N_{\zeta_{c_1}^e\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_{c_1}^e)}$ otherwise) with edge weight $\psi_{c_1\ell}^t$ ($\xi_{c_1\ell}^t$). Similarly, there exists an arc from $N_{i\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,i)}$ to $N_{\zeta_{c_2}^w\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_{c_2}^w)}$ with edge weight $\psi_{c_2\ell}^t$, or from $N_{\zeta_{c_1}^e\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_{c_1}^e)}$ to $N_{\zeta_{c_e}^e\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_{c_e}^e)}$ with edge weight $\xi_{c_e\ell}^t$. We continue the process until we can attach an arc from $N_{\zeta_{c_v}^w\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_{c_v}^w)}$, or $N_{\zeta_{c_v}^e\ell}^{t+\Phi(r, \zeta_{c_v}^e)}$, to $N_{j\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,j)}$. Finally, there exists an arc from $N_{j\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,j)}$ to M_j with edge weight $\kappa_{j\ell}^{t+\Phi(r,j)}$. This defines a path p from M_i to M_j in the TSLN- j . Using the same reasoning as before, the sum of the path weights is equal to the reduced cost of the flight-based variable $F_{r\ell}^t$ in the FBF formulation.

Proof of Proposition 5. We start with the proof for the forward algorithm. The complexity of the Bellman-Ford algorithm grows in the product of the number of nodes and edges in the network. The TSLN- j one node for each physical node, time period and lane and one node for each vertiport, hence an order of $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{T}||\mathcal{I}||\mathcal{L}|)$ nodes. Similarly, the number of edges grows in $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{T}||\mathcal{L}|)$. The Bellman-Ford is therefore $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{T}|^2|\mathcal{L}|^2|\mathcal{I}||\mathcal{C}|)$. In Algorithm 3, the Bellman-Ford algorithm is run $|\mathcal{V}|^2$ times, so the total complexity of the algorithm is $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{T}|^2|\mathcal{V}|^2|\mathcal{L}|^2|\mathcal{I}||\mathcal{C}|)$. Recall from Section 2 that $|\mathcal{I}| = \mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{V}|^{q_1})$ and $|\mathcal{C}| = \mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{V}|^{q_2})$, so the complexity of the algorithm can be written as $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{V}|^{2+q_1+q_2}|\mathcal{T}|^2|\mathcal{L}|^2)$.

By construction, the algorithm generates up to $|\mathcal{V}|^2$ paths at each iteration. Suppose that there exists a $F_{r\ell}^t$ with negative reduced cost. Let i and j denote its origin and destination vertiports. From Proposition 4, the shortest path on TSLN- j from M_i to M_j is negative and the algorithm correctly identifies the negatively priced variable $F_{r\ell}^t$. Vice versa, upon termination, there exists no path with a negative sum of edge weights in the TSLN- j , for all $i, j \in \mathcal{V}$. Again, due to Proposition 4, we know that there exists no flight-based variable $F_{r\ell}^t$ with negative reduced cost, thus providing a certificate of optimality in the FBF formulation.

For the backward algorithm, following the same reasoning as before, the time complexity of Algorithm 2 is $O(|\mathcal{V}|^{1+q_1+q_2}|\mathcal{T}|^2|\mathcal{L}|^2)$ due to the fact that we call the Bellman-Ford algorithm $|\mathcal{V}|$ times rather than $|\mathcal{V}|^2$ times. By construction, a forward path in the TSLN- j is equivalent to the a reverse path in the $\overline{\text{TSLN}}-j$, with the same total edge weight. Thus, Algorithm 2 correctly identifies variables with negative reduced cost or proves that none exists.

Appendix C: Details from Section 4

This appendix provides additional visualizations and details supporting the construction of the data-driven instances described in Section 4. In particular, we illustrate the vertiport locations used in the New York metropolitan area experiments, the corridor conjunction nodes derived from aviation infrastructure, the commuting patterns used to calibrate demand, and the weather scenarios used to model disruptions.

Vertiport and corridor conjunction locations We select 22 vertiport locations across the New York metropolitan area based on population density, proximity to major cities, and spatial coverage of the region. This approach follows clustering strategies commonly used in the AAM literature (Daskilewicz et al. 2018, Rajendran and Zack 2019, Willey and Salmon 2021, Rath and Chow 2022). The legacy corridor network relies on navigational aids used in the U.S. National Airspace System. These include VHF Omni-Directional Range (VOR) stations and non-directional beacons (NDBs), which define the conjunction nodes of the corridor network. Each vertiport is connected to its closest conjunction node to enable routing through the existing aviation infrastructure. Figure 15 shows the resulting vertiport locations and the spatial distribution of conjunction nodes in the New York region.

Figure 15 Vertiport locations and corridor conjunction nodes used in the data-driven instances for the New York metropolitan area.

Commuting patterns Passenger demand is calibrated using commuting flows from U.S. Census Bureau (2015). These data capture the distribution of commuting trips across the New York metropolitan area and serve as a proxy for potential AAM travel demand. Figure 16 visualizes the commuting flows between origin and destination regions used in the demand calibration process.

Figure 16 Visualization of commuting flows derived from U.S. Census data. Origins and destinations are shown in green and orange, respectively, and arc width represents commuting volume.

Weather scenarios Weather disruptions are generated using historical observations from aviation ground weather stations (Iowa Environment Mesonet 2023). Each three-hour planning window in the 2020 dataset is mapped to corridor nodes by associating each conjunction with its closest weather station. Nodes are considered unavailable when Instrument Meteorological Conditions (IMC) occur, defined as visibility below three statute miles or broken cloud coverage below 1,000 feet. The *Weather Severity Index* (WSI) measures the proportion of station–time observations under IMC conditions over the planning horizon. Figure 17 illustrates representative weather scenarios corresponding to different WSI levels. Figure 18 shows the empirical distribution of WSI values observed in 2020.

Appendix D: Details from Section 5

Visualization of AAM Operations in the New York metropolitan area. Figure 19 provides an illustrative visualization of AAM traffic patterns in the corridor network under different demand levels and numbers of vertical lanes. The figure highlights how traffic density and routing complexity increase as demand grows and additional lanes enable more flexible routing decisions.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge the guidance and feedback from Luis Alvarez. This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 1745302.

Figure 17 Examples of open (green) and closed (red) weather stations over a three-hour window for different WSI levels.

Figure 18 Distribution of Weather Severity Index (WSI) across three-hour periods in 2020.

Figure 19 AAM operations under low vs high demand and coarse vs. dense vertical lanes.